

Analysis of Carbon Monoxide in Low Concentrations using Uv-Visible Spectrophotometry

S. C. SRIVASTAVA*, S. SINHA, M. M. BHATTACHARYA
R. K. PAUL and R. V. K. SINGH

Central Mining Research Station, Dhanbad-826 001

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THE paper describes the detection and photometric analysis of 100–500 ppm of carbon monoxide by its colour reaction with aqueous ammonium molybdate solution.

Carbon monoxide forms a complex with ammonium molybdate giving a broad maximum at 338–343 nm. Since the nature of the complex is unknown, molar absorptivity was not calculated.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of A.R. grade. Ammonium molybdate (1%, w/v) was prepared in 1 : 3 nitric acid in distilled water. Fresh solution was prepared for each analysis as ammonium molybdate solution is unstable on storage.

Carbon monoxide was prepared by a laboratory method and subsequently estimated¹. No effect of other common gases such as methane, carbon dioxide etc. was noted. However, for analytical purpose, effects of the oxides of nitrogen, sulphur etc. had to be worked out to enhance the scope of the present technique.

Procedure : Air sample containing CO was taken in an evacuated sample tube. Sample tubes of 150 and 250 ml capacity were used for more and less than 500 ppm CO, respectively. Initial pressure of the sample tube, before and after gas sampling, was measured to calculate gas volume at NTP. In a 150 or 250 ml tube, 10 or 20 ml solution of ammonium molybdate was taken. Air sample thus collected was shaken for 5 min to develop colour and subsequently the contents transferred directly to an optical cell. Spectral measurements were performed on a Hitachi U-3400 spectrophotometer. Since absorbances of the coloured solutions were stable for nearly 1 h all the measurements were completed within this time. A straight-line relationship between 100 and 1000 ppm concentrations of CO against absorbance was generally observed and this served the purpose of computing CO in unknown samples.

For lower concentrations between 10 and 100 ppm, it was necessary to use a 1 lit sample tube. Total time required for an analysis was 10–15 min including time for preparation of the sample.

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Reference

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